

HEALTH RELATED BEHAVIOUR AND LIFE STYLE SURVEY OF MEDICAL STUDENTSDr. M. Wisam Mubashir*¹, Dr. Komal Tariq², Dr. Tuba Khalid³

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ABSTRACT

Background: A regular habit is essential for the preservation of health because healthy body has healthy mind. **Objective:** To determine the health related behaviour and lifestyle of the 1st Year MBBS students of Sheikh Zayed Hospital, Rahim Yar Khan. **Material and Methodology:** Cross-sectional observational study of 170 students was done in Sheikh Zayed Hospital, Rahim Yar Khan with their informed consent. A questionnaire was designed and data was collected in 30 days. Data was analyzed by Microsoft Excel version 2017. **Results:** A total of 170 students surveyed, 90 (52.9%) males and 80 (47.1%) females; students that took good care of their personal hygiene (95%) had regular sleep pattern of approximately 6-7 hours (45.3%) and those who performed physical activity for approximately two and half hours/ week (71.2%), had good eating habits (whom took fruits, milk, regular meal time) (90%). **Conclusion:** Most of the students had good personal hygiene and eating habits. Physical activity performed was adequate but there was room for improvement. Sleeping patterns were distribution.

KEYWORDS: Health, Personal hygiene, Physical activity, Sleep patterns, eating habits.**INTRODUCTION**

Personal hygiene is a public health tool that is used for disease prevention and health promotion in individuals, families and communities.

Winslow in 1920 observed that personal hygiene can be improved by educating individuals in communities on basic tips of achieving personal cleanliness through their organized efforts and informed choices.^[1] The focus of good personal hygiene is to prevent diseases, injuries and other health conditions through surveillance and promotion of healthy behavior in aspects relevant to human health. It may prevent health problems from happening or recurring by implementing educational programs, developing policies, administering services and conducting research.^[2]

An individual's diet and physical activity habits depend upon the following factors like familial and household influences, habit and price, health consideration, demographic factors, ethical concerns and social trends. Investigation of these in a population provides an insight that may be the mediators of motivation to change behaviors related to eating and physical activity. When a child and adolescent participate in at least 60 minutes of physical activity every day, multiple health benefits occur.^[3,4]

Regular physical activity builds healthy bones and muscles, improves muscular strength, reduces risk for developing chronic disease factors, improves self esteem, reduces stress and anxiety and improves academic performance.^[3]

Our research to study the personal hygiene among students of 1st Year MBBS Sheikh Zayed Hospital, Rahim Yar Khan is carried out to check out the status.

Objective

To determine the health related behaviour and lifestyle of the 1st Year MBBS students of Sheikh Zayed Hospital, Rahim Yar Khan.

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

Study Design: Descriptive cross-sectional study.

Duration of study: 30 days (December 2018 to January 2019).

Study Population: 1st Year MBBS students of Sheikh Zayed Hospital, Rahim Yar Khan. **Sampling Technique:** Non-probability convenient sampling.

Inclusion Criteria: 1st Year MBBS students. **Sample**

Size: 170 Students. **Data Collection Procedure:** A self-designed questionnaire was used to carry out survey after informed consent. **Data Analysis:** Microsoft Excel.

RESULTS

A total of 170 students surveyed, 90 (52.9%) males and 80 (47.1%) females; students that took good care of their personal hygiene (95%) had regular sleep pattern of

approximately 6-7 hours (45.3%) and those who performed physical activity for approximately two and half hours/ week (71.2%), had good eating habits (whom took fruits, milk, regular meal time) (90%).

Table 1: Gender distribution of 1st Year MBBS students. n=170.

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	90	52.9%
Female	80	47.1%
Total	170	100%

Table 2: Distribution of Body Mass Index (BMI) among 1st Year MBBS Students. n=170.

BODY MASS INDEX	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
<18.5 (UNDERWEIGHT)	38	22.4%
18.5-24.99 (NORMAL)	122	70.6%
25-29.99 (OVERWEIGHT)	8	4.7%
≥30.00 (OBESE)	4	2.3%
TOTAL	170	100%

Table 3: Address wise distribution of 1st Year MBBS Students. n=170.

ADDRESS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
HOSTELITES	102	60%
DAY SCHOLARS	68	40%
TOTAL	170	100%

Table 4: Frequency distribution of hostelite students of 1st Year MBBS on their view about satisfaction of living conditions of the college hostel. n=102.

ACTIVITY	FREQUENCY	
	MALES	FEMALES
SATISFIED	30 (29.4%)	15 (14.7%)
NOT SATISFIED	32 (31.4%)	25 (24.5%)

Table 5: Frequency distribution of 1st Year MBBS students on their view about promotion of health behavior by the college environment. n=170.

ACTIVITY	FREQUENCY	
	YES	NO
PHYSICAL ACTIVITY	121 (71.2%)	49 (28.8%)
NUTRITION	103 (60.6%)	67 (39.4%)

Table 6: Frequency distribution of 1st year MBBS Students on the basis of Personal Hygiene. n=170.

ACTIVITY	FREQUENCY	
	YES	NO
Hand washing before eating	160 (94.2%)	10 (5.8%)
Hand washing after going to toilet	162 (95.3%)	08 (4.7%)
Taking bath regularly	124 (72.9%)	46 (27.1%)
Brushing the teeth regularly	164 (96.5%)	06 (3.5%)

Table 7: Frequency distribution of 1st Year MBBS students on the basis of Sleep Pattern. n=170.

*GRADING	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
GOOD	77	45.3%
SATISFACTORY	37	21.8%
POOR	56	32.9%

***Grading**

To bed upto 10PM, wakening before fajar prayer = GOOD

To bed 10-12pm, wakening after prayer = SATISFACTORY

To bed midnight and onwards = POOR

Table 8: Frequency distribution of 1st Year MBBS Students on the basis of Physical Activity n=170.

PHYSICAL ACTIVITY	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
YES	73	42.9%
NO	97	57.1%

Table 9: Frequency distribution of 1st year MBBS Students on the basis Smoking. n=170.

SMOKING	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
YES	-	0.00%
NO	170	100%

Table 10: Frequency distribution of 1st year MBBS Students on the basis of Eating Habit. n=170.

ACTIVITY	FREQUENCY	
	YES	NO
TAKING BREAKFAST	156 (91.8%)	14 (8.2%)
TAKING MEALS REGULARLY	143 (84.1%)	27 (15.9)
EATING FRUITS	165 (97.1%)	05 (2.9%)
EATING FRIED FOOD	164 (96.5%)	06 (3.5%)
TAKING CAFFEINATED BEVERAGE PER DAY	55 (32.4%)	115 (67.6%)
TAKING ONE GLASS OF MILK OR YOGURT	67 (39.4%)	103 (60.6%)

DISCUSSION

Our study was compared with other studies conducted worldwide. A cross-sectional study was conducted, aimed to determine the hazardous health behaviour of first and last class medical students of "Erciyes University" Turkey between March–April 2012. Out of 339 medical students with a response rate of 91.6%, 240 (64%) being from 1st Class with mean ages (19.4+/- 1.5) years and 130(36%) students from the last class with mean ages (24+/-1.5) years. Males showed greater hazardous behavior. 64% of students under study did not perform physical activity (lasting thirty minutes five times a week). 13% did not sleep 7-8 hours daily. More than 1/3rd of the students did not consume cooked vegetable dishes. 1/4th did not consume fresh fruits and salads.^[5] A study was conducted aimed at investigating the relationship between physical activity, sedentary behaviour, sleep duration and body mass index-for-age (BMI-for-age) and HRQOL (Health related quality of life) among high school students in Tehran, Iran. Out of a total of 465 students, 48.8% were girls recruited from different socio-economic zones in Tehran. Greater than one-third (38.5%) were found to be overweight /obese. HRQOL scores were lower in girls compared to boys. Mean hours of daily sleep were found greater in girls (8.16+/- 1.27) hours vs. boys (7.73+/-1.22) hours. Both boys and girls led a sedentary life, not engaging in extracurricular activities.^[6]

A cross-sectional study was carried out amongst Medical students from the University Medical School of Szeged, Hungary. To observe and describe health risk behaviour

242 participants aged 18-31 years were selected. Response rate was 73%. In order of prevalence: excessive coffee drinking (35%), smoking (20.9%) and illicit drug use (5.1%).^[7]

A cross-sectional Youth Physical Activity and Nutrition Survey was conducted in 12 secondary schools, Guyana. 724 students in Form1 to four participated. 54% of students performing physical activity that made them sweat and breathe for about 20 minutes on three or more days. About half (48.7%) of the students played video games for one or more hours a day. 56.3% Students did not attend PE classes at school. About 12.6% students ate two or more cups of fruit and 12.9% of students ate vegetables, each day.^[8]

CONCLUSION

Medical students are conscious about their health and take good care of it despite their hectic schedule and sedentary lifestyle. Being medical students they are aware of health related issues and complications. So they do try to maintain their fitness.

Most of the students of 1st Year MBBS Sheikh Zayed Hospital, Rahim Yar Khan have good personal hygiene and good eating habits. Physical activity is not upto the mark and can be improved and their sleep pattern is distribution.

Recommendations

- In order to prevent unhealthy lifestyle behaviour, extra circular and health facilities should be increasingly be provided.
- Lectures and seminars should be conducted to increase health awareness.
- Nutritional Education can be provided to students to make better daily balanced diet choices.
- Increase consciousness of students towards health habits and general hygiene by using posters and brochures.
- Regular General physical examination should be conducted to observe any BMI (weight changes), nutritional and hygienic abnormalities.
- Inspection of physical training of students, and coordination in Physical Education.
- Annual and routine inspection of students can be conducted with a view to detect any defects in them and their follow up.
- Cafeterias in College should provide nutritionally healthy meals.

LIMITATIONS

- Students were reluctant to fill out the questionnaire, as they were not used to such activities.
- Some students were reluctant to give their height and weight, so their filled out their information randomly.
- A few students did not take it seriously and gave false information.

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